

Chemical Investigation of the Leaves of *Eugenia wallichii* Wight III

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Eugenia wallichii (Fam. Myrtaceae) is a large tree, growing abundantly in Sikkim, Khasia, Bhutan and Assam. Investigation on this species was undertaken because of chemotaxonomic interest. The isolation of friedelin, epi-friedelanol, betulinic acid and β -sitosterol from the bark of *E. wallichii* have been reported by us¹. The present work deals with the isolation of 1-dotriacontanol from the benzene extract of the leaves. Plant material for investigations was collected from Raja Bhat Khawa Forest, North Bengal.

Procedure: Air-dried, finely powdered leaves of *E. wallichii* (350 g.) was extracted with benzene in a soxhlet apparatus for 12 hr. The dark green residue obtained after the removal of the solvent was dissolved in small quantity of benzene and chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (80 g.) using petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), different mixtures of petroleum-benzene, benzene and benzene-ether mixtures as the successive eluents.

The petroleum eluates afforded red jelly like substances, whereas the petroleum-benzene and benzene eluates provided a solid (.15 g.), which on crystallisation from benzene melted at 89.5-90°. It developed no colouration with tetranitromethane. Its analysis corresponded with the molecular formula $C_{32}H_{66}O$ and it showed a peak in its IR spectrum at 2.95 μ , characteristic of hydroxyl group. Presence of this functional group was further supported by the preparation of its acetate, m.p. 74°. These data agreed fairly well with those reported² for 1-dotriacontanol, $CH_3 \cdot (CH_2)_{30} \cdot CH_2OH$. Mass spectrometric investigation registered a weak molecular ion peak at m/e 466 for the compound and revealed a fragmentation pattern expected in accordance³ with the normal straight chain aliphatic alcohol.

The red jelly like substance obtained from the petroleum eluates as mentioned earlier was dissolved in ether, treated drop by drop with alcohol, shaken and cooled in ice whereby yellowish-white solid separated out. It was crystallised from ether-ethanol mixture, and had m.p. 56-8°. Further work on this material, obtained only in traces, is in progress.

1. *This journal*, under publication.

2. "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", vol. III, Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1965, p. 1323.

3. R. A. Brown, W. S. Young and N. Nicolaidis, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 1653-4.

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